

IMPACT OF CELLULOSE FILAMENTS ON INTERLAMINAR PROPERTIES, FLAMMABILITY AND THERMAL DEGRADATION BEHAVIOUR OF POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Context & Motivation

- Cellulose fibres are a relatively new type of bio-sourced fibre which use was demonstrated to increase interlaminar strength (ILSS) of polymer matrix composites in published literature [1,2]
- Current FAA-certified polymer matrix composite materials are expensive (PEEK, PEI, PPS, etc.). Alternative polymers exist but typically possesses lower mechanical properties
- Cellulose-fibre reinforced polymer matrix composite (PMC) could be used to replace more expensive polymer for aircraft interior applications if they meeting strict requirements for fire, smoke, and toxicity (FST) properties
- Effect of biomass addition on flammability rating is yet unknown.

Objective

Evaluate the impact of cellulose fibres on interlaminar shear strength and flammability of unidirectional glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic

Manufacturing

Materials:

- PA6-FR:** Ultramid B3U, BASF (100-200µm films)
PA-6 w/ 10-15% melamine cyanurate
FAA-MFTH Chap1 compliant
- PA66:** KNF FlexPak (50µm films)
Used as reference material
- Glass fibres:** SE1200, Owens Corning
- Cellulose fibres:** FiloCell, Kruger Biomaterials
Diameter: 80-300nm
Length: 100-2000µm
Density: 1450 kg/m³

Testing

- Interlaminar shear strength: Short Beam Shear test
- Constituent content: Optical micrography, density measurement and pyrolysis
- Flammability rating: FAA-MFTH Chap 1 [3]
- Flame time: Time for the flame to self extinguish [FAA threshold: <15s]
- Burn length: Distance burned until flame self extinguishes [FAA threshold : <150mm]
- Thermal stability: Analyzed through thermogravimetry

Specimen manufacturing

- Film stacking compression molding
- Size: 305x305 mm
 - Mechanical test: 5mm
 - Flammability test: 1.5mm
- Fibre volume fraction
 - Mechanical test: 40-60% (see table 1)
 - Flammability tests; 70%

Results

- None of the specimen tested pass FAA-MFTH Chap.1
 - The use of FAA compliant polymer matrix does not guarantee FAA compliant polymer composite
 - All tested samples failed relative to the burn length and flame time criteria
- Use of flame-retardant additive significantly reduces ILSS (figure 1)
- Addition of cellulose fibres did not improve ILSS. In fact, ILSS was significantly decreased over reference sample at equivalent fibre volume fraction.
- Cellulose fibres have shown a tendency to increase sample flame-time and thus reduce burn-rate (Figure 2)
 - Slower burn rate seems to be attributed to endothermic decomposition as well as enhanced charring of cellulose fibres [4]

Figure 1: Material behaviour during short beam shear test

Table 1: Constituent content of samples for mechanical tests

System	V _f [%]	V _{CF} [%]	X _v [%]
PA6-FR 60Vf	62±1	-	1.3±0.4
PA6-FR 40Vf	37±2	-	1.0±0.5
PA6-FR + CF	40±2	1.95*	0.3±0.1
PA66	40±5	-	0.9±0.8

*Estimated

Average Thickness-normalized Flame Time

Figure 2: Normalized flame-time of the different polymer systems tested

References and Acknowledgments

- [1] Faruk, Progress in Polymer Science, 2017; [2] Goswami, Proceedings of the American Institute for Composites, 2017; [3] Federal Aviation Administration – Aircraft Materials Fire Test Handbook; [4] Sekiguchi, Y. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 1983